

Enhanced energy efficiency of photogalvanic cell with mixture of two dyes as photosensitizers in EDTA-DSS system

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Abstract : In this paper photocurrent and photo voltage generation using mixture of two dyes (Sudan Black-B+Azur-B) in liquid phase photogalvanic cell at different concentrations have been studied. Photogalvanic cells are aqueous phase electrochemical device capable of solar energy conversion and storage using alkaline solution of photosensitizer and reductant. The observed photopotential and photocurrent values in this system were 965.0 mV and 340.0 μ A respectively. The conversion efficiency of the system was observed 0.8157% and fill factor determined as 0.2585. The cell performance was observed 110.0 min in dark. The effects of different parameters on the electrical output of the cell were observed and current-voltage (*i-V*) characteristics of the cell were also studied.

Keywords : Photogalvanic effect, Sudan Black-B, Azur-B, EDTA, DSS, fill factor, conversion efficiency.

Introduction

Photogalvanic cells are solution based dye sensitized solar power conversion and storage devices, which are based on photogalvanic effect. Rideal and Williams¹ firstly reported this effect but it was systematically investigated and the term was first used by Rabinowitch²⁻⁴. Later on, this kind of work was followed by various notable workers all over world⁵⁻¹⁵.

Literature reveals that various workers have studied the harvesting of solar energy in various forms of solar cells and mixtures of dyes and surfactant but conversion efficiency and fill factor of photogalvanic cell are still low¹⁶⁻¹⁸. So the use of suitable photosensitizer (mixture of two dyes) with reductant in photogalvanic cell is needed for increasing electrical output and energy efficiency. Therefore, with the aim of getting enhanced energy efficiency and fill factor of photogalvanic cell, the use of new mixture of Sudan Black-B+Azur-B in EDTA-DSS system was planned to be carried out and results are reported in this paper.

Material and methods :

Chemicals and reagents : Sudan Black-B (Ases

Chemical Works, Jodhpur, India) and Azur-B (Ases Chemical Works, Jodhpur, India) used as mixture of photosensitizers (Schemes 1 and 2). Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (98% minimum Assay-purity, Ases Chemical Works, Jodhpur, India) used as reductant and dioctyl sodium sulphosuccinate (98% minimum Assay-purity, Ases Chemical Works, Jodhpur, India) used as surfactant in experiments. Concentration of solutions of Sudan Black-B+Azur-B mixture was 10^{-5} M, ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid 10^{-3} M and dioctyl sodium sulphosuccinate 10^{-3} M. All solutions

Scheme 1. Structure of Sudan Black-B.

Scheme 2. Structure of Azur-B.

except Sudan Black-B and Azur-B have been prepared in doubly distilled water and were kept in amber colored containers to protect them from direct sun light.

Experimental set up : A solution of mixture of two dyes; Sudan Black-B+Azur-B ($2.00 \times 10^{-5} M$), reductant EDTA ($1.64 \times 10^{-3} M$), surfactant DSS ($1.52 \times 10^{-3} M$) and 1 M sodium hydroxide were taken in an H-shaped glass tube which is blackened (by black carbon paper). The whole reaction mixture was diluted up to 25 ml by double distilled water. The arm with window acts as illuminated chamber [a shiny platinum foil electrode (as negative terminal) was immersed in limb] and other arm without window act as dark chamber [a Calomel electrode-CE (as positive terminal) was immersed in the other limb] of the H-tube. The pH of the solution was adjusted and measured by a digital pH meter the cell attained a stable potential in the dark after some time the limb containing a platinum electrode was exposed to a light source. A water filter was used to cut off thermal radiation. On illumination, the photopotential (mV) and photocurrent (μA) are generated by the system were recorded in digital pH meter and microammeter.

Absorption properties of pure and mixture of two dyes : Absorption spectra were recorded using ELICO SL 244 Double Beam UV-Vis Spectrophotometer with a matched pair of silica cuvettes. Sudan Black-B showed an absorption peak in the visible region at 593 nm, 553 nm in ethanol and water respectively and Azur-B showed an absorption peak in the visible region at 635 nm, 623 nm in ethanol and water respectively and absorption spectra of the mixture of two dyes were also taken. The combination of two dyes (Sudan Black-B+Azur-B) showed an absorption peak in the visible region at 653 nm, 662 nm in ethanol and water respectively. Later this mixture of dyes with concentration $1.52 \times 10^{-5} M$ kept constant and graph were taken while mixing surfactants of different concentrations (Fig. 1).

Mechanism of photocurrent generation : In illuminated region of the cell, a dye molecule excites in the triplet state (i.e. through inter-system crossing

Fig. 1. Absorbance spectra of dye and their mixture.

(ISC) collapses singlet state to excited triplet state) of mixture of Sudan Black-B and Azur-B photosensitizer. In particular, the presence of electron donating substances, certain molecules of dyes rapidly changes to colourless (“reduced”) form. The formation of dye is a reduced form and donates electrons to other substances, thus it returns to its oxidized state¹⁹. This way, the photogalvanic cell enables solar energy conversion into solar power with inherent storage capacity. On the basis of this photocurrent generation in photogalvanic cell be explained by the following mechanism schemes²⁰ :

Illuminate chamber (anode) :

At platinum electrode :

Dark chamber :

At counter electrode :

Here (SBB+AB), (SBB+AB)⁻, EDTA and EDTA⁺ are the dye (SBB+AB = Sudan Black-B+Azur-B), its leuco form, EDTA (reductant) and its oxidized form, respectively.

Results and discussion

Effect of variation of photosensitizer (mixture of two dyes), reductant (EDTA) and surfactant (DSS) concentration on the system : The variation in photopotential and photocurrent with the change in concentration of photosensitizer (mixture of two dyes; Sudan Black-B+Azur-B), reductant (EDTA) and surfactant (DSS) were studied in detail. The cell has total 25 mL (including Dye, EDTA, DSS, NaOH and doubly distilled water) solution. The effect of photopotential and photocurrent on the concentration of photosensitizer (mixture of Sudan Black-B+Azur-B), reductant (EDTA) and surfactant (DSS) is shown in Figs. 2, 3 and 4. The increase in cell output like photopotential and photocurrent observed with increase in concentration of the photosensitizer, reductant and

Fig. 2. Variation of photopotential, photocurrent and power with Sudan Black-B+Azur B concentration.

Fig. 3. Variation of photopotential, photocurrent and power with [EDTA] concentration.

Fig. 4. Variation of photopotential, photocurrent and power with [DSS] concentration.

surfactant up to $2.00 \times 10^{-5} M$, $1.64 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $1.52 \times 10^{-3} M$ respectively and beyond this concentration, the decrease in these parameters were observed (Table 1).

Thus, a maximum photocurrent (340 µA) and photopotential (965 mV) was observed for a particu-

Table 1. Effect of variation of Sudan Black-B+Azur-B, EDTA, DSS concentration and pHLight intensity = 10.4 mW cm⁻², Temp. = 303 K

Parameters	Photopotential (mV)	Photocurrent (mA)
[Sudan Black-B+Azur-B] × 10 ⁻⁵ M		
1.68	865	274.0
1.84	918	307.0
2.00	965	340.0
2.18	922	305.0
2.64	871	275.0
[EDTA] × 10 ⁻³ M		
1.58	842	278.0
1.61	909	308.0
1.64	965	340.0
1.67	921	304.0
1.70	838	276.0
[DSS] × 10 ⁻³ M		
1.48	846	274.0
1.50	912	306.0
1.52	965	340.0
1.54	918	304.0
1.56	839	272.0
pH		
12.70	858	278.0
12.74	925	311.0
12.78	965	340.0
12.82	921	308.0
12.86	863	276.0

lar value of photosensitizer (mixture of two dyes; Sudan Black-B+Azur-B), reductant (EDTA) and surfactant (DSS) concentration $2.00 \times 10^{-5} M$, $1.64 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $1.52 \times 10^{-3} M$ respectively, above which a decrease in electrical output of the cell was observed. As the intensity of light reaching the dye molecules near the electrode decreases due to absorption of the major portion of the light by dye molecules present in the path, higher concentration of EDTA will promote back electron from dye molecule to reductant molecule and also hinder the motion of the dye molecule toward the electrodes and higher concentration of DSS will hinder the motion of dye molecules towards the electrodes respectively. Concentration of photosensitizer, reductant and surfactant lower than $2.00 \times 10^{-5} M$, $1.64 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $1.52 \times 10^{-3} M$ resulted into a fall in photopotential and photo-

current because fewer photosensitizer (dye-mixture of Sudan Black-B+Azur-B) molecules are available for the excitation and consecutive donation of the electrons to the platinum electrode, fewer reductant (EDTA) molecules to donate electrons to dye molecules and fewer surfactant (DSS) molecules would be available for electron transfer and stability of dye molecules respectively.

Effect of variation of pH on the system : Electrical parameters of cell are recorded on an optimum pH 12.78. The increase in cell electrical parameters like photopotential and photocurrent was observed with increase in pH up to 12.78, and beyond this pH, the decrease in these parameters was observed (Table 1). The performance of the cell is poor in acidic medium due to proton attachment in dye and reductant, leading poor electron donating power of double bond – Hetero atoms of dye and reduced at Pt electrode. Thus, a maximum was observed for a particular value of pH (12.78), above which a decrease in electrical output of the cell was observed, because at high pH, OH⁻ ions (comes from NaOH) which may combine with cationic reductant (formed on electron donation from reductant to dye) hindering the reductant to attain the original form which leads to poor performance of cell. The effect of photopotential and photocurrent on the variation of initial pH is shown in Fig. 5.

Effect of diffusion length : The effect of variation of diffusion length (distance between the two electrodes) on the current parameters of the cell (i_{\max} , i_{eq}) and initial rate of generation of the photocurrent studied using H-shaped cells of different dimensions. It was observed that in the first few minutes of illumination there was sharp increase in the photocurrent. The conductivity of electro active species depends on its population between electrodes. The increase in photocurrent with increase in diffusion length up to 45 mm, and beyond this diffusion length, the decrease in photocurrent was observed (Table 2). Thus, a maximum photocurrent was observed for a particular value of diffusion length (45 mm), above which a decrease in photocurrent of the cell was observed, as the photocurrent of dye increases due to increase in

Fig. 5. Variation of photopotential, photocurrent and power with pH.

Fig. 6. Variation of current parameters with diffusion length.

Table 2. Effect of diffusion length

[Sudan Black-B+Azur-B] = $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$

[EDTA] = $1.64 \times 10^{-3} M$

[DSS] = $1.52 \times 10^{-3} M$

Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}

Temperature = 303 K

pH = 12.78

Diffusion length (mm)	Maximum photocurrent i_{max} (µA)	Equilibrium photocurrent i_{eq} (µA)	Rate of initial generation of photocurrent (µA min ⁻¹)
35.0	368.0	352.0	14.72
40.0	373.0	346.0	14.92
45.0	378.0	340.0	15.12
50.0	384.0	335.0	15.36
55.0	389.0	329.0	15.56

volume of solution between electrodes. As diffusion length decreases, concentration gradient factor reduces and photocurrent decreases (Fig. 6).

Effect of electrode area : The effect of variation of Pt electrode area on the current parameter of the cell was studied using platinum foil electrode of different size. Under the observed effect of electrode area, the current parameter was found highest for electrode area 1 cm^2 . Decrease in cell current parameter was found for electrode area larger than 1 cm^2 (Table 3), and (i_{eq}) was found all most independent to the change in electrode area of the cell.

Current-voltage (i - V) characteristics of the photogalvanic cell : The photogalvanic cell with Sudan Black-B and Azur-B – EDTA-DSS system, the (cur-

rent-voltage) characteristics was studied. After charging the cell, the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current (i_{sc}) of the photogalvanic cells were measured under the condition of light, with the help of potential (measured by digital pH meter keeping the circuit open) at different direct current (measured by micro ammeter keeping the circuit closed) and by varying resistance (calculated by Ohm law) of the circuit. It was observed that current-voltage (i - V) curve deviated from their regular rectangular shape (Fig. 7).

The cell was operated at highest power (P_{pp}) at corresponding external load, current (i_{pp}) and potential (V_{pp}) to study its performance by observing change in current and potential with time and the fill-factor

Table 3. Effect of electrode area

Sudan Black-B+Azur-B-EDTA-DSS system	Electrode area (cm ²)				
	0.70	0.85	1.00	1.15	1.30
Maximum photocurrent i_{max} (μA)	369.0	373.0	378.0	384.0	388.0
Equilibrium photocurrent i_{eq} (μA)	350.0	446.0	340.0	335.0	328.0

Fig. 7. Current-voltage (i - V) curve of the cell.

was calculated using the following formula :

$$\text{Fill factor } (\eta) = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}} \quad (1)$$

where V_{pp} and i_{pp} represents the value of potential and current at power point, respectively and V_{oc} , i_{sc} are open circuit voltage and short circuit current, respectively. The value of fill factor calculated as 0.2585 and the power point of cell (pp) as 84.83 μW.

Cell performance and conversion efficiency : The performance of the photogalvanic cell was studied in term of half change time ($t_{1/2}$) and conversion efficiency (CE) in dark. The time taken for fall in the power of the cell to its half value of power at power point is called $t_{1/2}$ (which is a measure of storage capacity of the cell). The cell performance is shown

in time-power curve (Fig. 8). It was observed that the cell can be used in dark for 110 min. Conversion efficiency of the cell was determined as 0.8157% by formula :

$$\text{Conversion efficiency} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{A \ 10.4 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}} \quad (2)$$

where V_{pp} , i_{pp} and A are photopotential at power point, photocurrent at power point and electrode area respectively.

Fig. 8. Performance of the cell.

Conclusions

The mixture of two dyes Sudan Black-B and Azur-B in EDTA-DSS combination used for photogalvanic conversion of solar energy. The conversion efficiency,

Table 4. Comparative results of reported dye mixture

Mixture of dyes	Conversion efficiency	Fill factor	Photopotential (mV)
Methylene Blue+Thionine	0.430	0.49	752
Methylene Blue+Azur-B	0.1165	0.18	732
Methylene Blue+Toludine Blue	0.5398	0.49	742
Sudan Black B+Azur	0.8151	0.25	965

$t_{1/2}$ and fill factor of this cell were recorded as 0.8157%, 110.0 min and 0.2585 respectively which is comparatively higher than the single dye systems in photogalvanic cell with same EDTA-DSS system. Reason may be the wide absorption of shift radiations by mixture of two dyes as compared to a single dye. Furthermore, photopotential and energy efficiency is higher than other dye mixtures reported by other workers (Table 4)²¹⁻²³. Therefore, it may be concluded that photogalvanic cell with mixture of dyes are more efficient in view of efficiency and storage of solar energy.

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